

Quality evaluation of government open data sets in Argentina using the HEVDA Validation Tool

*Evaluación de la calidad de los conjuntos de datos abiertos
gubernamentales en Argentina utilizando la herramienta de validación*

HEVDA

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AUTORES: Roxana Martínez^{1*}

Claudia Pons²

Rocío Rodríguez³

Pablo Vela⁴

DIRECCIÓN PARA CORRESPONDENCIA: ing.roxana.martinez@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This work consists of measuring the quality of the datasets available on the web portal of the official public and national site of the country of Argentina. This research proposes to carry out a quality study applying the Open Data Quality Validation Tool (HEVDA), this tool implements quality metrics that measure the selected dataset, which results in an analysis of the flaws detected in it; for example, it allows detecting if there are errors, incomplete records, types of redundancy, etc. To explain the framing of this work, a survey of the aspects that are involved in this context is shown: open government, open public data, as well as government transparency. On the other hand, it shows the importance of maintaining the quality of the shared data, since it will be reused in different data sources and software, so this research focuses on the necessary aspects that favor the reading and

¹Magister en Tecnología Informática, Interamerican Open University (UAI).

²Doctor en Ciencias Informáticas, Interamerican Open University (UAI).

³Doctor en Ciencias Informáticas, Interamerican Open University (UAI).

⁴Doctor en Ciencias Informáticas, Interamerican Open University (UAI).

understanding of the data sets published on government portals, which allows generating public opinion and showing traceability of the management of government resources.

Keywords: *Open Data, Public Data, Quality in datasets, Open Government.*

RESUMEN

Este trabajo consiste en medir la calidad de los conjuntos de datos disponibles en el portal web del sitio público oficial y nacional del país de Argentina. Esta investigación propone realizar un estudio de calidad aplicando la Herramienta de Validación de Calidad de Datos Abiertos (HEVDA), esta herramienta implementa métricas de calidad que miden el conjunto de datos seleccionado, lo que da como resultado un análisis de las fallas detectadas en el mismo, por ejemplo, permite detectar si existen errores, registros incompletos, tipos de redundancia, etc. Para explicar el encuadre de este trabajo, se muestra un relevamiento de los aspectos que están involucrados en este contexto: gobierno abierto, datos públicos abiertos, así como transparencia gubernamental. Por otro lado, muestra la importancia de mantener la calidad de los datos compartidos, ya que serán reutilizados en diferentes fuentes de datos y software, por lo que esta investigación se centra en los aspectos necesarios que favorecen la lectura y comprensión de los conjuntos de datos publicados en portales gubernamentales, lo que permite generar opinión pública y mostrar la trazabilidad de la gestión de los recursos gubernamentales.

Palabras clave: *datos abiertos, datos públicos, calidad en datasets, gobierno abierto*

INTRODUCCIÓN

In the governmental sphere, the concept of the open government paradigm is booming. This topic includes the importance of different initiatives that are focused on a better relationship between citizens and the national State. Its main objective is that there are different means available to encourage citizen participation and thus, the different actions of the government are reflected to explain clearly and transparently.

Some authors define open government as “a public policy that groups together the concepts of transparency, participation, and collaboration of citizens in public policies where government information and data play an essential role” (Cobo, 2020). Others mention a government that “proposes a new form of public management in which alliances

are created between citizens and governments at all levels to achieve the best results. Furthermore, it includes promises associated with the development of TIC (Technology of the information and communication), and within these, it projects changes in the relationships between social actors, such as the interaction between governments and citizens, especially from its participatory dimension” (Chaves, 2020). An interesting approach that some authors do is that Open Government “should not be conceived only as an element to promote government transparency, accountability, and public trust, but also as a dynamic mechanism that is useful to generate economic and social value in the public and private sectors” (OCDE, 2015).

The Open Government had an important growth in recent years, which led several organizations to dedicate themselves to promoting this new political model. One of the most recognized organizations worldwide is the Open Government Partnership (OGP, 2021), which works to promote a government that is more accessible, responsive, and responsible to citizens, and thus improve the relationship between people and their government, as this brings exponential long-term benefits for everyone. This movement is linked to the new framework of public governance and a renewed state methodology, so within this context, the open government constitutes a frame of reference to align the compliance of the Objectives of the 2030 Agenda (Naciones Unidas, 2020). These Sustainable Development Objectives were proposed to provide different government targets to put an end to poverty, protect the planet, and improve the lives and prospects of people around the world. “Given the recent progress made by the 15 countries in the region that are currently part of the Open Government Partnership, it seems important to move towards the idea of an open State, that is, towards an institutional effort to promote and articulate policies and strategies in matters of transparency, access to information and open data, accountability, citizen participation and civic collaboration and innovation beyond the executive branch, towards the legislative and judicial branches, as well as towards the sub-national and local levels of government” (Naser, 2017). Although this open movement has been debated since 1970, the concept spread in 2009 when the President of the United States, Barack Obama, formulated the Memorandum on Transparency and Open Government (White House, 2009).

The new paradigm point of view allows a transparent government to make information about its actions and plans available to citizens immediately, easily and free of charge. “By expanding access to public information, accountability is strengthened, and public debate is enriched while creating new opportunities to generate added value” (Buenos Aires provincia, 2017). Transparency within the context of Open Government consists of ensuring the right of all citizens, which is free access to public government information. In this way, a government can show, simply and clearly, the management performed, and thus promote active management.

Transparency can be of two types: passive or active, this depends on whether the information is requested on demand by a citizen or organization (Passive), or if the State makes it publicly available (Active).

Active Transparency: Active transparency is a concept in which the different public organizations must give access to information and have the responsibility to provide all this data through their institutional website, that is, periodically publish and spread relevant information in an accessible and open format.

Passive transparency: Passive transparency is associated with the right of access to information by citizens. This implies the guarantee of the right of access to information that all people have, as stipulated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (art. 19) (Naciones Unidas, 2021) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (art. 19, 2) (Humanos, 1976). It proposes an institutional means for citizens to request the information produced by the State.

This work is about active transparency.

Following next, the works related to this framework of investigation with the most relevant aspects of the open data quality are shown based on an analysis performed. Then, the proposal of the developed prototype is described, with an explanation of each metric and its relationship with the software. Afterward, the results obtained in the already stated research are presented, with the comparative analysis of aspects worked. Finally, the conclusions and future works are presented.

METHODOLOGY

Background Information

Tim Berners-Lee (5stardata.info, 2012) developed a 5-star model, in which he suggested a development scheme for the treatment and publication of Open Data. This considers in mind the format and structure of the data. Organizations such as Open Data Institute (ODI), present tools, Open Data Certificate (Certificate, 2021), which works based on existing standards and provides a simple evaluation of how well the data accomplish the best practices, to evaluate and recognize the sustainable publication of quality open data. Its objectives point to the legal, practical, technical and social aspects of open data publishing, providing data publishers with a best practice guide for optimal reuse of open data.

Various governments and organizations that encourage/promote the Open Government (MinTIC, 2020) (Support, Open Data, 2020) (Datos.gob.es, 2020), published guides of good practices to use of government public data, to promote the use of datasets and, in addition, have in mind some quality criteria of the quantitative type, such as applications to data opening, number of state organizations that open data, percentage of the strategic open data set that were published, number of data sets downloaded versus the number of published datasets or the number of datasets visited versus downloaded datasets. Other works point to the quality criteria oriented to interoperability, to provide guidance and good practices for the development of data opening strategies that comply with the main quality standards and open data interoperability of the best-qualified countries in international indexes such as the Open Data Barometer, the Global Open Data Index and Our Data Index. Moreover, in the information domain guides of the Frame of Reference of the Ministry of Information and Communications Technologies (MinTIC), the ISO 25012 data quality model, the Open Data International Charter, and the Interoperability Frame for the Digital Government (Gobierno de Colombia, 2020).

Regarding quality, there are works (Oviedo Blanco, 2016), (Beltrán, 2017), (Ibanez Gonzalez, 2019), (Rodríguez Rojas, 2017), (Arizo, 2016) that focus on establishing criteria and classifications of quality levels of open data. Some analysis scenarios are oriented from the reuse of open and public data. On the other hand, some quality measurement techniques are based on the concept of the availability of data in open portals, to promote an adequate level of availability for their consumers. Besides, mechanisms are defined to evaluate the maturity of an open portal, through metrics to measure quality, such as, for example, traceability, completeness, and conformity. Other works (Abella, 2018) guide the

evaluation of quality in the analysis of the Berners-Lee five-star model and other factors that help to evaluate reuse. In addition, they propose that the relationship between the demand for open data and the dispersion of distributions and data sets available on a certain topic can be analyzed. Therefore, it is interesting to study the result of whether to concentrate the information in few more complete and manageable data sets could help to improve the efficiency in the publication of these.

Other more recent authors (Cadena-Vela, 2019), (Vela, 2019), (Leonangeli, 2019) present an analysis of the current status in the field of open data, as well as international standards and good data quality practices to propose a reference framework that enables the publication of open data with an appropriate level of quality. Other works that are still under research (Barrera, 2020), are oriented to quality, through the analysis of the information published in the geoportals, to measure the degree of reuse of their geospatial data sets, that is, because there are no specific standards of quality analysis. In addition, other studies (Royo-Montañés, 2019) indicate that most portals seem to function as mere data repositories, neglecting those aspects that promote the use of data by the non-expert public, for example, the definition of the metadata used. Other authors (Schieferdecker, 2012) focus on the quality of open data based on the context that software presents, for example, treatment of different types of data in software.

Research Framework

At present, there are many open data portals in different countries of the world, that is why having various guides that orientate the constant improvement of quality is essential, but, moreover, it is vital to have tools that allow rapid validation to facilitate the detection of shortcomings or issues related to integrity, redundancy, among others, as explained in the previous section.

Having quality open public data available will allow citizens and organizations to have greater trust in data sources and monitoring of administrative processes of the State, as well as structuring and standardizing them for different interactions with each other, for example, software interoperability.

Based on the analysis made, this work proposes a software tool that allows knowing the quality of a dataset through the calculation of quality metrics proposed in the application. This developed tool is called HEVDA (Spanish acronym for *HErramienta de Validación de*

calidad de Datos Abiertos. i.e., Open Data Quality Validation Tool). The HEVDA tool shows a quantitative quality result of the open data analyzed with it.

For the data sample, the 5 most relevant government open data portals of the Argentine Republic were considered. For each portal, 25% of the total amount of datasets made available was taken as a sample. That is, for a case that has a total of 41 datasets, its 25% was taken, this being 10 datasets as a sample for this study and so on with each government website.

In the following sections, the results obtained from the completed research are presented and analyzed.

HEVDA

Technical Aspects: The developed tool allows the validation of the different suggested metrics for a set of open data in CSV formats (Comma Separated Variable). Although HEVDA allows an automatic analysis to be obtained, it does not modify the source dataset, but rather provides a detailed analysis that serves as a practical guide for correcting it. Some technical aspects are:

Integrated Development Environment (IDE), Visual Studio Community 2019 (Microsoft, 2021), is a complete tool for programming, debugging, testing, and implementing solutions on any platform. Another reason for which it was selected is that it has a friendly programming environment, and, in addition, its community version is free. On the other hand, there are forums at the platform's technical support level and backing material.

Regarding the programming language, C # was used, which is the object-oriented programming language, with ASP .NET, which is the framework provided by Microsoft for web development. Specifically, C # was used together with ASP .NET for the server-side coding, and HTML, CSS, JS for the client-side. As a web server, IIS (Internet Information Services) version 10.0.19041.1 was used.

Functional Aspects: The general functionality of the software consists of selecting a dataset file of the CSV format type and executing the validation of the proposed metrics. For the choice of the type of format, studies were taken into account (Martínez, 2020), in which the government portal Argentina Unida (Argentina Unida, 2021) was taken as a sample case with its 973 datasets till July 2020. Their results concluded that the most used format is the

CSV type with 61.6% of use, it is for this reason that the HEVDA tool works with the CSV type format.

The detailed functionalities of the programmed tool are:

Detection and detail of cases that do not comply with the valid format for the decimal data type.

Estimated calculation of the data types of the validated dataset fields.

Calculation of the quantity and percentage of duplicate records.

Detail of duplicate records.

Calculation of the quantity and percentage of the complete records.

Calculation of the number of cases that have fields with Null records (No Data or spaces in the fields).

Calculation of the number of cases that have fields with empty records (Without Data and with spaces in the fields).

Calculation of the number of cases that have fields with Unavailable records (With data indicating N/D, N/A, NULL, -, - -, -).

Displaying the details of the cases with Null, Empty, and Unavailable records.

Calculation of the number of columns affected with special characters and their corresponding detail.

Calculation of the number of columns affected with repeated values in the same field (domain of values).

Detail with search filters for the dataset fields and words of the detected fields in cases where there were records with repeated values for the same field (domain of values).

Calculation of the quantity and percentage of cases detected with redundancy between the values of the fields for the same record.

Search filter for the cases detected with redundant data between the values of the fields for the same record and its corresponding detail.

Estimation of the number of IDs identified in the columns of the dataset, and their visualization.

Calculation of the number of columns affected with possible trivial fields and their identification.

In Figure 1 sector A, the initial HEVDA screen is shown, containing the file selection option and a button “Analyze Open Data Dataset” to start the validation. On the other hand, there is a vertical bar on the left with the categories of metrics, critical and non-critical, which can be displayed with a click to access their corresponding established metrics. This is shown in Figure 1 sector B for critical metrics and Figure 1 sector C for non-critical metrics.

Once the file that has to be analyzed is selected, the tool will display a report for each one of the metrics.

Implemented metrics

Metric 1 - Treatment of decimal numbers: It indicates the number of cases that are detected for the validation of the type of decimal numbers.

For example, “There are 3 cases with decimal numbers incorrectly loaded or incorrect decimal separator with, (comma)”. In addition, a link “click to see details of records” is available, which visualize the cases affected. Subsequently and in a complementary way, an estimation analysis is shown that the tool calculates, to detect the calculation of the data types of the fields of the analyzed data set; This is visualized through a grid that contains: the names of the titles of the columns of the dataset, and the types of data detected (according to the internal algorithm proposed in the HEVDA tool). The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality in the treatment of interoperability between software, which is why it is necessary to identify the type of data for a correct exchange of data between various programs.

Figure 1. HEVDA Tool Home Screen.

Metric 2 - Duplicate Records: It indicates the number of cases detected with duplication of records, showing the amount affected over the total records of the dataset. For example: “Number of cases detected with duplication of records: 11 of 1400”. Based on that, the percentage of duplicate records affected is presented, being: “Percentage of duplicate records: 0.79%”. In addition, there is the option to view the detail of the records.

The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that detecting cases of duplication of records favors better use and analysis of the data. Data without redundancy allows defining data structures and providing simplicity in the treatment of the different processes that use them, for example, Extraction, Transformation, and Loading, ETL (Extract, Transform and Load) processes for adequate data management with multiple sources.

It is important to focus on the fact that “duplicate elements within a sampling frame have undesirable effects, such as an overestimation of population totals, or the generation of biased samples to carry out new studies” (Alba Cuellar, 2011). It is for this reason that their identification is necessary on time.

Metric 3 - Incomplete and Complete Data: It shows the number of complete and incomplete records and their corresponding percentage. On the other hand, a data grid as a summary is observed, with the 3 proposed classifications discriminated by dataset columns: Null, Empty, and Not available.

For example: “The Null classification has a quantity of X cases, registered for the column “province_id”; For the Empty classification, a case is indicated for the column “country”; For the classification of Not available: the cases with data indicating “N/D”, “N/A”, “NULL”, “-”, “- -” or “--” are considered.

The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that the lack of values in the dataset fields provides a fine line to confusion and/or misinterpretation of cases since many of these open data are used in dynamic tables, statistical algorithms, open data histories (DATA, 2021), graphical visualizations or software developments. Like the case detection metric for Duplicate Records in the previous section, for the analysis of this metric, quantitative data quality measures are considered.

For this approach that guarantees quality in data, the aspect of dimensions is oriented to the concept of Completeness. “The level of data completeness reflects the degree to which all the attributes of a piece of data are present, which allows a clear vision of the integrity of the elements to be studied” (Everywhere, 2021).

Metric 4 - Invalid Characters: This proposed metric allows for the identification of the special characters of the analyzed data set. It could include the affected character, and the record number of the dataset, as well as the name of the column/field in which it appears.

The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that it is important to locate these types of characters in order not to alter the identification and analysis of the values contained in the data sets. The great problem that entails that the data is presented with invalid characters, will suppose a loss of information and, consequently, a loss of objectivity of what is being analyzed as a result.

Metric 5 - Redundancy for the domain of a column: It consists of the redundancy measurement in the domain of values of a column. That is, it is the number of times that the same value of a field is repeated in each row for the same column.

For example, for the name of the column "country" of a dataset, the data "Argentina" is found 5 times.

The tool displays the number of detected columns that have repetition in their data is displayed. The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that within the quality standards, recommended by the government site of open data of the Argentine Republic (Datos P. d., 2021), it is suggested that the entities that appear among the data of a textual field must have a unique description. Therefore, the importance of detecting cases of equal values, to know if they are well aggregated or should be modified so that they comply with the same description. Therefore, it is suggested that every mention made of a given entity should be made using the same character string each time (datos.gob.ar, 2021).

Metric 6 - Redundancy between fields of the same row: This proposed metric allows identifying the number of cases with fields that have equal values (repeated / redundant) for the same record of the analyzed dataset.

The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that there is an elementary principal for data quality, which is not to repeat the same values in

more than one column for the same row in the dataset. That is, each column provided in the data set must be well defined and described since it represents a specific value in the logical and representative analysis of the data in open format.

“One of the operations that any database developer faces most frequently is the detection and treatment of duplicate data, that is, finding several times the same records in a table, due to problems in the design and inconsistencies of the database or to locate certain subsets of data with conditions that are repeated within the same table” (brujo, 2015). To improve data quality, it is necessary to eliminate redundant or repetitive information. Duplication of data can lead to mistakes or logical errors in the final analysis that can be the consequence of not having an integrated approach in the dataset logic.

Metric 7 - ID detection: This aspect analyses the estimation of fields with ID, detecting the fields that contain 'id', 'id_' and/or '_id', as much in uppercase as in lowercase letters. For example: “We have found 5 columns that represent ID (country_id; id; province_id; category_id; Certifier_id)”.

The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that the fields that contain "ID" in their descriptions are used with numeric values and represent a code or unique value of integers that is not null, and, in addition, they are implemented to uniquely identify each of the rows in the data set. It is necessary to quantify the number of fields for this type, since, although they are identifiers, citizens and/or organizations that access this data set may not interpret the meaning of the numerical code that is shown, that is, in many cases, the datasets are part of an analysis of various statistical studies, which fail to detect the meaning and/or usefulness of the traditional nomenclature of ID codes. This would be solved if the corresponding data dictionary is attached to the official site from which the dataset was extracted, to understand the fields of the dataset, and, above all, the meaning of these ID fields.

Although open datasets must contain well-defined, organized, and justified data, as a good practice, the government site of open data of the Argentine Republic (Argentina Unida, 2021), suggests the use of an identifier field in the dataset, because “it is usually useful for the univocal identification of variables in some systems or applications, but not in most cases” (Modernización, 2019). It should be clarified that not all data sets have ID fields, this is optional.

Metric 8 - Trivial fields: consists of the verification of redundant fields for the same column in all its records. To do this, the number of columns affected is displayed over the total number of columns in the dataset.

For example: Field: country_id, Value of the field: 32, and Field: country; Value of the field: ARGENTINA.

That is, for the field "country_id", the value "32" was found, and for the field "country", the value "ARGENTINA" was detected in all its data.

The basis for adopting this metric and its contribution to the measurement of quality is that a duplicate record occurs when the same data has been entered more than once, so it is important to detect that some fields/columns have the same data. The discovery of these cases will allow knowing if there are fields that can be omitted in the dataset, since these could be indicated as data in the name of the dataset.

For example: if a country = Argentina field is detected in all the records, then the dataset should contain "Argentina" in its name, where: Dataset called "Registered cases of Covid-19", could be called "Registered cases of Covid-19 in Argentina".

In the next section, the scope of the sample used for the study of the datasets verified with the HEVDA tool is presented.

Data Collection

The first step was to select the open data sets to be validated with HEVDA. For this, the 5 most relevant Argentine governmental open data portals were taken as a sample: Open Data Portal of the Argentine Republic (Argentina Unida, 2021), Open Data Portal of the Ministry of Health of Argentina (Datos D. A., 2021), Open Data Portal of the Chamber of Deputies of Argentina (Diputados, 2021), Open Data Portal of the Ministry of Justice and Human Rights of Argentina (Datos P. d., 2021), and Open Data Portal of the City of Buenos Aires (Buenos Aires Ciudad, 2021).

It should be clarified that the choice of these government portals is due to the fact that they are the ones with the largest number of datasets in Argentina and, in turn, are the most relevant.

For each portal, the Categories were identified, and for each one of these, the datasets were downloaded in the open format of the CSV type to be validated with the HEVDA tool. From each portal, 25% of its total datasets were considered as a sample.

Table 1 shows the number of datasets from each of the government portals and their corresponding 25% as a sample taken for validation.

To identify the 25% of the sample, in case of having a result with a greater decimal part equal to 0.5, an additional dataset is taken. For example:

From an open data portal that has 61 datasets in total, its 25% sample is 15.25, so 15 datasets were considered. So that the choice of the 15 datasets is random, it was considered to take a uniform quantity per category.

Table 1. Number of datasets for each of the government portals.

Open Data Portal (released until January 13, 2021)	TOTAL datasets to release	25% of total datasets (quantity)
Ministry of Health of Argentina (Datos D. A., 2021);	41	10
Chamber of Deputies of Argentina (Diputados, 2021);	29	7
Ministry of Justice and Human Rights of Argentina (Datos P. d., 2021);	61	15
City of Buenos Aires (Buenos Aires Ciudad, 2021)	398	99
Argentine Republic (Argentina Unida, 2021);	1013	253
Total amount of datasets		384

If the public data portal has 10 Categories, a dataset of each Topic will be taken into consideration, plus 1 extra dataset of 5 Topics in order to consider the 15 datasets as a sample.

Another possibility that is presented is having to take, for example, 5 datasets from each Group, but there is a Group that has only 2 datasets, so more datasets were selected from the following groups (according to the order of appearance in the portal) for cover the sample.

As shown in Table 1, the 25% sample resulted in analyzing a total number of 384 datasets.

RESULTS

This section shows all the results obtained for the tests of the 384 datasets validated with the HEVDA tool. The analysis of results is presented in different classifications based on general results, results discriminated by critical and non-critical metrics, and types of blockers.

Structural analysis

The datasets that have some blocking characteristics are discarded from the analysis due to the belonging of some type of structural non-compliance aspect for which they cannot be treated by the tool.

The cases are identified below:

The file has a double character “(quotation mark).

The file does not meet the same number of columns in each of its records.

The file does not comply with the CSV format of the separator (comma).

The file does not have the first row of titles/names of the columns of the dataset.

The file has repeating title names.

For this study, the total number of blocking datasets is 113, representing 29%, and the number of non-blocking datasets is 271, representing 71% of the total of 384 datasets validated with the application developed. Therefore, it can be suggested to detect these cases when preparing a dataset to avoid future issues in the interoperability of public government datasets.

Table 2 shows the percentage established for each type of blocker among the 113 datasets (29.43% of the analyzed sample), detected with the HEVDA tool. It is observed that the first place is for Type 3 (“The file does not comply with the CSV format of separator (comma);”), which is the most representative with more than half of blocking types with 57.52%. Followed by Type 1 (“The file has a double character (quotation mark)”) with 15.93%, then by Type 2 (“The file does not meet the same number of columns in each one of its records”) with 14.16%, then Type 4 (“The file does not have the first row of titles of the columns of the dataset”) with 11.50% and the last one the Type 5 (“The file has names of repeated titles”) with 0.88%.

General results of the metrics

This section shows a comparison of the results obtained based on the analysis of the number of datasets that comply or non-comply with, separated by the 8 proposed metrics. The number of datasets surveyed is 271, that is, 70.57% of the sample used since 113 datasets were found, that is, 29.43%, with blocking characteristics, which is why they are discarded from the analysis due to the membership of some type of unfulfillment aspect for which they cannot be handled/processed by the developed tool.

Table 2. Number of datasets with structural problems.

Type	Detail	Percentage datasets
1	The file has a double character “ (quotation mark);	15,93%
2	The file does not meet the same number of columns in each one of its records;	14,16%
3	The file does not comply with the CSV format of separator (comma);	57,52%.
4	The file does not have a first row of titles/names of the columns of the dataset;	11,50%
5	The file has names of repeated titles;	0,88%

Table 3 shows the percentage in each cell discriminated for non-compliance with metrics. The metric that is most fulfilled in validated datasets is Metric 2 with 65.10% (duplicate records), on the other hand, the most unfulfilled metric is Metric 5 with 55.73% (Redundancy in the domain of values of a column).

In Figure 2, the comparison of metrics represented by a bar graph is shown, where for each metric 2 bars are shown, the first one corresponds to the unfulfillment of the metrics and the second one to the fulfillment. Metric 2 (duplicate records) has 250 datasets, it is the most accomplished, followed by Metric 1 (validation of the decimal data type) with 209 datasets, Metric 8 (trivial fields) with 186 datasets, and Metric 7 (detection of ID values) with 182 datasets, being these the cases with the least difficulties encountered. Another one of the aspects that are observed are the metrics that are least achieved, that is, the first bar in each metric, as it is the case of Metric 5 (redundancy of values in the domain of a column) with 214 datasets, followed by Metric 4 (invalid characters) with 141 datasets and Metric 3 (incomplete data) with 116 datasets, being these the 3 most relevant cases of data quality unfulfillment.

Table 3. Unfulfillment datasets by metrics.

Type Number	Percentage that comply	Percentage that non-comply
METRIC 1: Decimal Numbers	54,43%	16,15%
METRIC 2: Duplicate Records	65,10%	5,47%
METRIC 3: Incomplete Data	40,36%	30,21%
METRIC 4: Invalid Characters	33,85%	36,72%
METRIC 5: Redundancy in the	14,84%	55,73%

Type Number	Percentage that comply	Percentage that non-comply
domain of values of a column		
METRIC 6: Redundancy between fields of the same row	44,01%	26,56%
METRIC 7: Detection of ID values	47,40%	23,18%
METRIC 8: Trivial Fields	48,44%	22,14%

Figure 2. Verification of open data quality metrics.

Through this research and the proposed metrics, they can be classified into critical and non-critical metrics.

Critical Metrics: They contain those metrics that allow detecting data problems of a priority type for a correct analysis of results with datasets, such as redundancy issues, missing content in records, or erroneous data. In other words, it is necessary to keep these aspects in mind, since their presence does not favor a correct study of the available data.

Non-Critical Metrics: Contain those metrics that could represent content problems in the dataset. Its detection is focused on possible estimates of cases of mistakes and trivial data, as well as discoveries of combined redundant data (between fields and dataset records) that could lead to inconveniences in the analysis of a data set.

A graph is included in Figure 3 that represents the study of critical metrics (from 1 to 4 inclusive) with the percentage that represents the number of unfulfillment cases for them. That is, of the 384 validated datasets, 830 cases of unfulfillment cases of data quality metrics were found (being that the same dataset may or may not comply with more than one metric), of which 340 cases with unfulfillment of critical metrics were detected. Although it does not exceed half of the total cases detected (830 total cases of unfulfillment), it is a fairly high number. Regarding critical metrics, according to Figure 3, the most unfulfilled critical metric is Metric 4 (invalid characters) with 41.47%, followed by Metric 3 (incomplete data) with 34.12%, then Metric 1 (validation of the decimal data type) with 18.24% and finally Metric 2 (duplicate records) with 6.18%.

Figure 3. Percentage of cases with unfulfillment: Critical metrics and Non-Critical metrics.

Figure 3 shows a graphic with the non-critical metrics (from 5 to 8 inclusive) with the percentage that represents the number of non-compliance cases for them. That is, of the 384 validated datasets, 830 cases of non-compliance with data quality metrics were found (being that the same dataset may or may not fail to comply with more than one metric), of which 490 cases with unfulfillment of non-critical metrics were detected. This value exceeds more than half of the total cases detected (830 total cases of non-compliance), so that, in unfulfillment issues, more cases of non-critical than critical metrics were found. According to Figure 3, the most unfulfilled non-critical metric is Metric 5 (redundancy in the domain of values of a column) with 43.67%, followed by Metric 6 (redundancy between fields of the same row) with a 20.82%, then Metric 7 (detection of ID values) with 18.16% and finally Metric 8 (trivial fields) with 17.35%.

DISCUSSION

In this article, various literature sources were exposed that support the importance of measuring the quality of open government data, as developed in the section “Background Information” in which research on the quality of the datasets is presented. These works were analyzed to identify metrics that can measure and evaluate aspects about the open data files. Also, different international organizations and institutions that work every day to raise awareness and improve the openness of government data in aspects of Open Government were surveyed. Some of these works analyze and propose measurement standards and good practices for the evaluation of the datasets available in open data portals. These studies consider some issues oriented to the measurement of files on public websites and release statistics on the number of files downloaded, number of data sets, licenses, metadata, or quality criteria oriented to software interoperability and file format, but in none of these cases, a study is made of the content of the government datasets, that is, what values they have and what state they are. On the other hand, various authors were presented who propose publication standards for opening files and viewing content for the citizen, but not a detailed analysis of the content of open data sets. Other research works are focused on raising awareness of this new paradigm, which is why they provide a repository of geographic locations of countries with open data portals around the world (Open Data Inception, 2016), (Portals, 2011), but they are only direct accesses and do not present an analysis of the datasets.

Regarding measurement criteria, some international organizations (Global Open Data Index, 2017) present indices that arise from the analysis of a set of aspects for each country, for example, it is shown that only 11% of the data sets worldwide are open. Although this analysis is interesting, only the points referring to licenses are studied, if the files are readable by a machine, if they can be downloaded from the official portal, if they are updated, among others, but this is not analysis from the point of view of the content that the datasets have. Other studies on the impact of open data initiatives are: the Open Data Barometer (World Wide Web Foundation, 2019), the Open Data Inventory (ODIN) (Open Data Watch, 2020), and the Open Data Index of Argentine Cities that presents a ranking of the current state of the release of data in an open format in the country's municipalities (Open Data Census, 2021), these works are cases in which it was observed that they

evaluate the coverage and openness of data to continue with open data policies, but neither it performs an internal analysis of the content of the datasets, but rather its study is oriented to the availability of the general structure of the files.

From the approach of evaluation models, there are international organizations such as the International Open Data Charter (Xhardez, 2020) and (Pinto, 2004) that propose as evaluation methodology, some parameters that can be evaluated on the content, accessibility, functionality, navigability, up to date and design. Also, it is important that the evaluation is oriented to the use of a guide of good standard practices (Indart, 2020) to facilitate interoperability and accessibility (Pasini, 2018) to maintain the principles of openness. From the quality aspect of the dataset content, there are studies carried out in Argentina, Brazil, and Paraguay (Nicolás & Catachura, 2020) that measure quality based on their content, for example, incomplete data, obsolete and invalid data, among others. This leads us to think of another type of approach to quality issues, since a quality vision is not presented from the file, but from the content of the file.

In this article, great importance is given to having aspects that must be addressed and reconciled among various sectors of the public administration in this paradigm of government transparency, the implementation of quality standards in open data will favor various state organizations that not only provide public data to citizens but also to other state entities worldwide. Based on the studies carried out, the authors found that there are major problems, on the one hand, it could be observed that there are various drawbacks in the structures of the datasets available in the open data portals and that the data has several shortcomings, For example, incomplete or empty data inside or problems of structures in which the number of columns and others is not delimited correctly, the other major drawback is that there are no control or validation tools for the datasets, due to the fact that there are few investigations that focus their study on the content and quality of the data provided.

Based on the findings of this study, it is possible to affirm that the validation and analysis tools for open data quality metrics are necessary in order to maintain the validity and integrity of the content. These tools favor a high possibility of obtaining a reliable analysis about a certain context. This makes it possible to obtain a study on the points to consider and to have a "state of health" of the data sets, which could be improved, in case of

detection of faults, for example, redundancy, lack of fields, lack of names that logically identify each field in the data set, among others. A detection tool allows the veracity of the content to be used and reflected in a study with added value to the citizens. Another contribution that is presented in this work is the importance of defining various metrics that analyze different properties of the content, such as repetitions, types of redundancies, character validations and others, in order to understand the data, avoiding leading to false studies on wrong or dirty data. It should be noted that the quality metrics proposed by the HEVDA tool that was developed in this work, allow mitigating possible errors in the treatment of data sources, in addition, this is a positive point for collaboration in software interoperability, so that open data can be reused. An interesting point to keep in mind is that the HEVDA validation tool could be used in the open portals of the different state government agencies, in order to provide a study to help those organizations that want to make their open public data available.

This would raise awareness about the importance of the value of the data to carry out valid studies, as well as keeping in mind that organizations will be able to validate their datasets before being published on their websites and thus, be able to mitigate or avoid certain errors in their contents.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The role of the technology is fundamental to promote access to information, citizen collaboration, and the availability of the aspect of transparency in this context. Therefore, it is necessary to consider certain essential facilitators for an adequate agreement between the government and the citizens. Due to the importance of the quality of open data according to the previously mentioned, it is vital to focus on various metrics that help measure the quality of open public data exposed as datasets in governmental portals.

As shown in previous sections, for the results of this study it is observed that of the 384 datasets compiled, there are only 6.51% (25 datasets) that comply with all the validations of the proposed metrics. This leads us to think about the long way to go in matters of good practices and the quality of the data available on government websites.

As a result, and contribution of this research, the HEVDA validation tool allows a better collection of state data sources, to know if they can be correctly used by software processes by state organizations. It is important that governments perform this validation

before uploading their datasets, to their portals and make them available, and thus, anticipating possible deficiencies in the data. It is worth mentioning that datasets without errors, will help to strengthen trust between citizens and the State.

As future lines of research, the scope and implementation of more quality metrics will continue to be studied, as well as their development in the HEVDA tool and thus analyze and detect more problems in datasets and improve both the content quality and interoperability.

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